

Enhanced catalytic performance of La₂O₃ promoted Co/CeO₂ and Ni/CeO₂ catalysts for effective hydrogen production by ethanol steam reforming

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ABSTRACT

Cobalt- and nickel-based catalysts were synthesized by the co-impregnation method of the ceria support with aqueous solution of the active phase and promoter precursors and evaluated in steam reforming of ethanol (SRE) reaction. The stability of Co/CeO₂ and Ni/CeO₂ catalysts was effectively improved by the addition of ~2 wt% of La₂O₃ promoter as the carbon deposition rate was reduced which results from an increase in an active phase dispersion and from strengthening of a metal-support interactions. Whereas the La₂O₃ promoter influences on the rate of carbon deposit formation, its type and a degree of graphitization depends on the metal active phase. Highly ordered carbon deposit encapsulating the active sites was mainly formed on the surface of cobalt-based catalysts. Whereas SRE reaction over nickel-based catalysts leads to formation of long filaments carbon with a lower degree graphitization. Temperature of 460 °C was sufficient to obtain complete ethanol conversion for 21 h of SRE process over Ni-0.1La/CeO₂ sample and to maintain high selectivity to H₂ (88%) and CO₂ (68%) over this time. For Co-0.1La/CeO₂ catalyst, the higher temperature of 500 °C was required to sustain its stable operation but selectivity to H₂ and CO₂ was even higher, 94% and 88%, respectively.

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1. Introduction

Over the years, people have depended on traditional energy sources such as oil, coal, and natural gas, for manufacturing and living. Unfortunately, these fossil fuel resources are limited and geographically concentrated in some regions of the world, while countries in other regions need to import them. Moreover, the ongoing consumption of fossil fuels is creating serious environmental problems. Because of mentioned energy crisis, global warming and climate change, development renewable energy sources remains around global interesting. Finding ways to meet the energy demands with simultaneously addressing the environmental impacts associated with energy use in the future represents a major challenge to humanity [1–3]. Solar, wind and tidal sources are renewable energies but they are unstable and dependent on the seasons. Whereas bio-fuels, such as for hydrogen production, can even be more efficient than conventional fuels when consumed in fuel cells. Biofuels offer many advantages, such as sustainability, low net emission of

greenhouse gasses, development of emerging regions and security of supply. However, an effective and economical environmentally friendly biofuel is still the subject of several studies. In this context, ethanol is very attractive for the production of hydrogen due to its wide availability since it can be produced from the several biomass sources, its relatively low cost and the high hydrogen production capacity of the process per molecule of ethanol reformed [4–7].

Hydrogen may be generated from ethanol by steam reforming (SRE) (Eq. (1)).

However, one of the main barriers of this process is the catalyst deactivation that occurs mainly due to carbon deposition on the catalyst surface, which may lead to decrease in catalytic activity and selectivity toward hydrogen. Therefore, the feasibility of SRE process requires the development of catalysts that are active and highly selective toward hydrogen, and also with high stability and low impact for coke formation [8,9]. Several metallic active phase have been used for the catalytic SRE process because of their ability to break the C–C bond; mainly cobalt, nickel and noble metals such as rhodium, palladium ruthenium, platinum and iridium. However,

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besides, the active phase, the support, if it exists, can also affect the product distribution during ethanol conversion reactions because of the influence on the active phase dispersion and its reducibility. Moreover, in the case of redox supports like ceria, their high oxygen mobility promotes the mechanism of carbon removal, which in turn contributes to the high stability of the catalysts on ethanol conversion reactions [8,10,11]. On the other hand, thermal stability of ceria is poor, its surface area drops drastically at elevated temperature, leading to the decrease of its redox property and oxygen storage capacity on the surface of ceria. Therefore, it is necessary to improve the thermal properties of ceria and modify the ionic mobility by replacement of cerium with different cations of varying size and/or charge that leading to the formation of a defective fluorite structures solid solution. The doped ceria increases the surface properties and sintering temperature of the sample to higher temperatures [12–14]. The lanthanum-doped ceria has been reported for an important role for the enhancement of the structural and catalytic properties of CeO₂-based system [12,14–17].

To our knowledge, only a few studies have evaluated promoted with La₂O₃ ceria supported cobalt- or nickel-based catalysts in the SRE reaction. According to Abd El-Hafiz and Ebiad [14], the incorporation of La³⁺ into ceria lattice at Ce⁴⁺ sites led to formation of solid solution and its impregnation with cobalt salt solution allowed to obtain Co/CeO₂-La₂O₃ catalyst which exhibited complete ethanol conversion at lower temperature and higher deactivation resistant under SRE conditions in comparison with Co/CeO₂ catalyst. Doping of CeO₂ with La₂O₃ (Ce/La = 0.2) prevented not only the sintering of ceria but also influenced on the amount and morphology of carbon deposition. Also Carvalho et al. [15] reported that the catalysts with the same composition, namely Co₃O₄/La₂O₃/CeO₂ catalysts synthesized by the one-step polymerization method, performed better in SRE reaction than catalysts composed of only two oxides, Co₃O₄/CeO₂ and Co₃O₄/La₂O₃. The mixture of three oxides led to the formation of the Ce(La)_xO_x solid solution and the larger amount of this solid solution promoted the dispersion of metallic cobalt, decreased the carbon depositions, hindered the formation of graphitic carbon and increased selectivity to the desired products, hydrogen and carbon dioxide. The optimum amount of the La₂O₃ promoter for this catalyst containing 20 wt% of cobalt active phase was equal to 12 mol%. According to Xue et al. [16], both the amount of nickel and lanthanum markedly affected the catalytic performance of Ni_aLa_bO_y/10CeO₂ catalysts prepared by impregnation method of CeO₂ with Ni_aLa_bO_y precursor solution. The best performance under SRE conditions with complete ethanol conversion and high selectivity to hydrogen was obtained for Ni₁La₁O_y/10CeO₂ catalyst and this Ni/La/Ce = 1/1/10 M ratio correspond to 2.89, 7.3 and 72.28 wt% for nickel, lanthanum and cerium, respectively. It was suggested that lanthanum addition led to formation of active LaNiO₃, stabilized the NiO phase and increased the specific surface area. The anti-coking ability of the Ni₁La₁O_y/10CeO₂ catalyst was attributed to an appropriate concentration of NiO. Also Liu et al. [12] prepared LaNiO₃ with perovskite structure loaded on ceria support catalyst by using impregnation method which allowed to obtain highly dispersed particles of metallic nickel derived from reduction of LaNiO₃. The resistance to carbon formation in the case of this catalyst was attributed to the formation of La₂O₂CO₃ species under the SRE conditions acting as the main carbon scavenger Whereas citrate complexing method led to the catalyst consisting of Ce(La)_xO_x solid solution and NiO particles highly dispersed on it. In the case of this catalyst, the strong interaction between NiO and Ce(La)_xO_x solid solution was beneficial to inhibit the aggregation of NiO particles, and the abundant of oxygen vacancies existed in Ce(La)_xO_x solid solution was in favor of carbon elimination from catalyst surface. The results revealed that the preparation approaches had a great impact on the structure of catalyst and despite the same La/Ce = 0.45/0.55 M ratio and nickel content equal to 12 wt%, catalyst prepared with citrate

complexing method displayed better activity and stability. By comparing the two catalysts, it was deduced that oxygen vacancy had better ability to remove the deposited carbon than La₂O₂CO₃.

Given the potential of these systems, there have been few efforts to synthesis effective Co-0.1La/CeO₂ and Ni-0.1La/CeO₂ catalysts for hydrogen production in SRE process. These studies are combining of three factors, ensuring the obtainment catalytic materials with appropriate properties for application in SRE process, such as use of transition metal as the active phase, support with the redox properties and the rare earths metal oxide as the promoter. Because the literature [12,14–16] indicated that addition of only large amount of La₂O₃ promoter into Co/CeO₂ and Ni/CeO₂ catalysts was tested until now in SRE process, this work focuses on the effect of small amount of La₂O₃ additives on catalytic performance of cobalt- and nickel-based catalysts. Even the low amount of lanthanum on the catalyst surface is expected to enhance not only catalyst stability but also catalyst activity. In this aim, the cobalt- and nickel-based catalysts with molar ratio of La/Co(Ni) = 0.1 were prepared by co-impregnation method which in addition of being simple preparation method is also cheap and one-step. Because ethanol-to-water molar ratio of bioethanol produced by fermentation of sugars from plants is between 1:7 and 1:12 [18], the unusual high reactants ratio of 1:12 was chosen to these studies. For its steam reforming, the necessity of higher energy consumption for evaporation of water is compensated by the lower energy consumption obtained from: (i) less purification steps; (ii) lower working temperatures. As it is well known, the global energy balance would be considerably improved when bioethanol is used in process using water as reactant (such as reforming) to produce hydrogen for fuel cell, instead of using the energy to remove all water after fermentation [18,19]. The effect of La₂O₃ promoter was evaluated in terms of physicochemical properties, ethanol conversion, hydrogen selectivity and stability of cobalt- and nickel-based catalysts. Moreover, the effect of temperature on catalytic properties of Co-0.1La/CeO₂ and Ni-0.1La/CeO₂ catalysts was also examined.

2. Experimental

2.1. Samples synthesis and characterization

The Co/CeO₂ and Ni/CeO₂ catalysts were prepared by impregnation of the commercial nano-dispersed ceria support (<25 nm, Aldrich) in the presence of CA as reported elsewhere [20–25]. The Co-0.1La/CeO₂ and Ni-0.1La/CeO₂ catalysts with La/Co and La/Ni molar ratio equal to 0.1 were prepared by co-impregnation of the commercial nano-dispersed ceria support (<25 nm, Aldrich) with a solution of Co(NO₃)₂ × 6H₂O, La(NO₃)₃ × 6H₂O and CA or Ni(NO₃)₂ × 6H₂O, La(NO₃)₃ × 6H₂O and CA (the molar ratios of (Co + La)/CA or (Ni + La)/CA was 1/1). The La₂O₃/CeO₂ sample with lanthanum amount corresponding to this used to obtain Co-0.1La/CeO₂ and Ni-0.1La/CeO₂ catalysts was prepared by impregnation of the commercial nano-dispersed ceria support (<25 nm, Aldrich) with a solution of La(NO₃)₃ × 6H₂O and CA. After impregnation, precursors of all samples were dried at 110 °C for 12 h, then calcined at 650 °C with the heating rate of 2 °C min⁻¹ up to the calcination set point and maintained for 1 h at that temperature. The amount of the Co(NO₃)₂ × 6H₂O and Ni(NO₃)₂ × 6H₂O precursors was adjusted to reach a corresponding nominal metal loading of 10 wt% in all catalysts.

The BET surface area and porosity were obtained from nitrogen adsorption-desorption isotherms at -196 °C using ASAP 2405N (Micromeritics) on samples previously outgassed at 200 °C.

Metallic phase dispersion was measured by hydrogen chemisorption using the ASAP 2020 apparatus (Micromeritics). Prior to the hydrogen chemisorption, all samples were reduced in hydrogen flow for 1 h at 600 °C and degassed at the same temperature until a

final pressure lower than 10^{-5} torr was attained. Adsorption of hydrogen was carried out at 130 °C. The metallic surface area was calculated assuming a stoichiometry of Co(Ni)/H = 1/1 and that each cobalt/nickel atom of hydrogen occupies 0.065 nm².

The cobalt, nickel and lanthanum real content was determined by X-ray fluorescence method using a Canberra 1510 fluorescence spectrometer.

The X-ray diffraction patterns were recorded on non-reduced, reduced and used in SRE catalysts using Empyrean X-ray (PANalytical) diffractometer, performed at 40 kV and 25 mA, with a secondary monochromator with Cu K α radiation at a wavenumber of $\lambda = 0.154$ nm.

Temperature-programmed reduction experiments were carried out with a the AutoChem II 2920 (Micromeritics) equipped with a TCD. Prior to reduction experiments, the samples (50 mg) were thermally treated under air stream at 650 °C to remove water and other contaminants. TPR profiles were obtained by heating the samples under 10% H₂/He flow (30 mL·min⁻¹) from RT to 750 °C at a linearly programmed rate of 10 °C min⁻¹. The water vapour formed during reaction was removed in a cold trap (immersed in a liquid nitrogen-methanol slush) placed before the thermal conductivity detector.

Total oxygen storage capacity (OSC) was investigated by the temperature-programmed oxidation (TPO) experiment carried out with the AutoChem II 2920 (Micromeritics). Prior to the main experiment, the catalyst sample (0.1 g, 0.3–0.6 mm) was treated with the 6% H₂/Ar mixture, at the temperature of 600 °C for 1 h and next it was cooled down to RT. The TPO measurement was performed using 5 %O₂/He and heating of the catalyst sample from RT to 600 °C with the temperature ramp of 10 °C × min⁻¹. The signal was detected by thermal conductivity detector (TCD).

The quantity of coke deposited on the used in SRE process catalysts was determined by the thermogravimetric method using the TG121 microbalance system (CAHN), measuring the mass loss in the used catalysts during oxidation. Each sample was previously heated up to 600 °C for 1 h in helium (10 °C min⁻¹, 70 mL/min) to remove volatile compounds adsorbed on catalyst surfaces. Approximately 10 mg of used in SRE reaction catalyst was heated under air flow from RT to 800 °C at a heating rate of 10 °C min⁻¹ and the weight change was measured. Quantification of the carbon formation rate (CFR) on catalysts was calculated according to the equation [7]:

$$CFR = \frac{m_{carbon}}{m_{usedcatalyst} \times t} \quad (1)$$

where:

m_{carbon} - is the mass of carbon deposited on the catalyst calculated from TG; $m_{usedcatalyst}$ - is the mass of the catalyst, t - is the time of the reaction of steam reforming of ethanol.

The SEM images were taken using a FIB-SEM Crossbeam 540 FEG (Zeiss) with an acceleration voltage of 1.8 kV. For SEM observations, the samples were prepared by drying the solution of catalyst diluted in 98% ethanol dropped on carbon tape at room temperature.

The TEM and STEM images of catalysts were obtained in scanning/transmission electron microscope TALOS F200X (FEI Company), equipped with field emission gun (X-FEG), HAADF detector and EDS spectrometer. Microscopic studies of the catalyst were conducted at an accelerating voltage of the electron beam equal to

200 kV. The mapping was conducted in the STEM mode by collecting point by point EDS spectrum of each of corresponding pixels in the map. The collected maps were presented in the form of a matrix of pixels with the color mapped significant element and the intensity corresponding to percentage of the element.

2.2. Catalytic activity and stability measurement

The catalytic performance for SRE was carried out in a Micro-activity Reference unit (PID Eng & Tech.) under atmospheric pressure in a fixed-bed continuous-flow quartz reactor.

The catalytic bed, 100 mg of the catalyst with 0.1 g, 0.3–0.6 mm grain size diluted at the weight ratio of 1/25 with the same size of quartz in order to avoid temperature gradients and hot spots was placed in the reactor with a coaxially centered thermocouple. Prior to the reaction, the catalyst was heated in argon flow (100 mL/min) up to 600 °C (10 °C min⁻¹), followed by reduction *in situ* at 600 °C for 1 h with hydrogen flow (100 mL/min). Next, the sample was brought down to the reaction temperature (420, 460 or 500 °C) in a flow of argon, purging hydrogen from the system. The mixture H₂O/ethanol with molar ratio of 12/1 was feed from a mass controller (Bronkhorst) to an evaporator (150 °C) and the reactant vapors, without diluting with any inert gas, were fed to the reactor at a flow rate of 100 mL min⁻¹. The space velocity was maintained at 60 000 mL/g h. The inlet and outlet lines of the reactor were heated to 150 °C for complete vaporization of reactant species.

The reaction products were analyzed with an on-line two gas chromatographs. One of them, Bruker 450-GC was equipped with two columns, the first filled with a porous polymer Porapak Q (for all organics, CO₂ and H₂O vapour) and the other one – capillary column CP-Molsieve 5 Å (for CH₄ and CO analysis). Helium was used as a carrier gas and a TCD detector was employed. The hydrogen concentration was analyzed by the second gas chromatograph, Bruker 430-GC, using a Molsieve 5 Å, argon as a carrier gas and a TCD detector. Argon, introduced out of the reactor, was used as an internal standard. Because argon flow rate in each steam reforming test was fixed, based on the argon content in outlet, it was possible to calculate the selectivity to products in each experiment.

The conversion of ethanol (X_{EtOH}) and conversions of ethanol into individual carbon-containing products (X_{CP}) were calculated on the basis of its concentrations before and after the reaction:

$$X_{EtOH} = \frac{C_{EtOH}^{in} - C_{EtOH}^{out}}{C_{EtOH}^{in}} \times 100\% \quad (2)$$

$$X_{CP} = \frac{n_i C_i^{out}}{\sum n_i C_i^{out}} \times 100\% \quad (3)$$

where:

C_{EtOH}^{in} - is the molar concentration of ethanol in the reaction mixture (mol%); C_{EtOH}^{out} - is the molar concentration of ethanol in the post-reaction gas mixture (mol%); C_i^{out} - is the molar concentration of carbon-containing product in the post-reaction gas mixture (mol %); n_i - is number of carbon atoms in carbon-containing molecule of the reaction product.

The selectivity of hydrogen formation was determined as:

$$H_2 \text{selectivity} = \frac{C_{H_2}^{out}}{C_{H_2}^{out} + 2 \times C_{CH_4}^{out} + 2 \times C_{C_2H_4}^{out} + 2 \times C_{CH_3CHO}^{out} + 3 \times C_{(CH_3)_2CO}^{out}} \times 100\% \quad (4)$$

where:

C^{out} - is the molar concentration of the hydrogen-containing products in the post-reaction gas mixture (mol%).

The carbon balance was within $\pm 7\%$ for all catalytic runs.

In order to calculate the TOF values, the same apparatus were using as described in detail above. Small amount of ~ 7.0 mg of catalyst diluted with quartz at the weight ratio of 1/25 and the mixture $\text{H}_2\text{O}/\text{ethanol} = 12/1$ at a flow rate of 150 mL min^{-1} without diluting with any inert gas were used in order to obtain low-ethanol conversion under SRE conditions at 420°C . TOF was calculated taking into account the ethanol conversion that was taken after 180 min of SRE process. The ethanol conversion was kept below 10%.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Characterization of fresh catalysts

The BET surface area and porosity values of cobalt- and nickel-based catalysts are shown in Table 1. Introduction of La_2O_3 insignificantly changes the BET surface area of prepared samples and it slightly increases in the presence of La_2O_3 . Also pore volume and pore size are not significantly affected by the addition of the rare earth oxide to the catalyst. Similar results were obtained by Liu et al. [12] who suggested that addition lanthanum element can suppresses the sintering of CeO_2 particles. According to Xue et al. [16], La^{3+} with big radius of 0.11 nm can expand structure of ceria leading to the higher specific surface area.

Also chemical composition of catalysts are shown in Table 1. The cobalt content of the prepared cobalt-based catalysts is lower than the nominal value of 10 wt% and is ~ 7.5 wt% for both samples. Whereas the nickel loading is very close to the nominal value and in the case of both nickel-based catalyst is ~ 9 wt%. Both catalysts promoted with La_2O_3 contains ~ 2 wt% of lanthanum.

High active metal dispersion and large active metal surface area are generally believed to be crucial in achieving high catalytic activity and stability in SRE reaction catalyzed by cobalt- and nickel-based catalysts. Therefore, these values were determined by classical hydrogen chemisorption for the Co/CeO_2 , $\text{Co-0.1La}/\text{CeO}_2$, Ni/CeO_2 and $\text{Ni-0.1La}/\text{CeO}_2$ catalysts and shown in Table 1. For both cobalt- and nickel-based samples, the promotion of the catalysts with La_2O_3 , leads to a much larger active metal surface area and higher cobalt/nickel dispersion compared to the unpromoted catalysts. Whereas the dispersion is very similar for both $\text{Co-0.1La}/\text{CeO}_2$ and $\text{Ni-0.1La}/\text{CeO}_2$ catalysts ($\sim 9\%$), $\text{Ni-0.1La}/\text{CeO}_2$ catalyst exhibits the largest active metal surface area among all studies catalysts. These results confirm that La_2O_3 is a promoter for SRE reaction because it can prevent sintering of the active metal [4].

In addition, surface characterization by nanoscale elemental STEM-EDS mapping was also used to determine the surface distributions of cobalt and nickel elements on the Co/CeO_2 , $\text{Co-0.1La}/\text{CeO}_2$, Ni/CeO_2 and $\text{Ni-0.1La}/\text{CeO}_2$ catalysts. It is important to bear in mind that the electron microscopy observations were made on the Co_3O_4 or NiO phases, after impregnation, drying, and calcination,

but before reduction. During reduction, the oxides phase will transform to the metallic phase. Some fine-scale changes in the catalyst particle morphology are to be expected during the reduction process [26]. Nevertheless, Fig. 1a–d shows a STEM micrograph and complementary mapping of the prepared catalysts. It can be found that both cobalt and nickel elements are highly dispersed onto the ceria support in the case of all catalysts. When considering EDS spectra one should note that signals for $L\alpha$ Ce (4.837 eV) and $L\alpha$ La (4.645 eV) lines are very close to each other. In the case of this study, the intensity of lines, originated from lanthanum were in the noise level. Resulting situation has seriously affected the collected EDS maps giving the wrong impression of a homogeneous distribution of La on the surface of CeO_2 . Due to this, in presented STEM-EDS maps the distribution of La was omitted.

The XRD patterns of the calcined catalysts are shown in Fig. 2a–d (A). Respective of the formulas, all samples have fluorite face-centered CeO_2 crystalline phase [5,27–29]. Moreover, for cobalt-based catalysts, the reflections attributed to cubic phase spinel Co_3O_4 crystalline structure are visible at $2\theta = 31.3^\circ$, 36.8° , 44.8° and 65.3° [5,30,31]. Whereas three reflections of the nickel-based catalysts provide typical diffraction pattern for the cubic phase of NiO observed at $2\theta = 37.2^\circ$, 43.2° and 63.1° [28,32]. Compared with Co/CeO_2 and Ni/CeO_2 catalysts, lanthanum promoted samples display the broader and weaker diffraction peaks corresponding to Co_3O_4 and NiO species than those of unpromoted samples, indicating the formation of smaller size of Co_3O_4 and NiO crystallites [33]. The average crystallite size of Co_3O_4 , NiO and CeO_2 obtained by the Scherrer equation is showed in Table 2. The crystallite size of CeO_2 , however, remains almost constant regardless of the lanthanum addition. Diffraction peaks attributed to lanthanum species are not detected in the XRD patterns of $\text{Co-0.1La}/\text{CeO}_2$ and $\text{Ni-0.1La}/\text{CeO}_2$ samples possibly due to the low concentration of lanthanum (Table 1). Moreover, lanthanum species can exist in amorphous phase. According to Navarro et al. [34], the presence of lanthanum phases at a very low concentration and/or an amorphous state cannot be discarded because of the detection limit (~ 4 nm) of the XRD technique. On the other hand, no reflections assigned to lanthanum species but the presence of $\text{Co}_3\text{O}_4/\text{NiO}$ phases points to the possible existence of small amount of $\text{LaCoO}_3/\text{LaNiO}_3$ perovskite structures which cannot be detected possibly due to a dilution effect as was suggested by Alifanti et al. [35] and Zuo et al. [36]. The calcination conditions, however, i.e. too low temperature and too short time, seem to be inefficient to form perovskite structure. The formation of La_2O_3 is much more probable because according to Mekhemer and Balboul studies [37], La_2O_3 can be obtained by the thermal decomposition of $\text{La}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \times 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ salt in an atmosphere of air in the temperature of at least of 650°C . It suggests that in the case of lanthanum-promoted catalysts, lanthanum species exist as La_2O_3 , highly dispersed on the catalyst surface. Because the lattice parameters of ceria (Table 2) for all catalysts do not change in relation to that of the pure ceria phase (0.5411 nm) it allow to exclude the formation of solid solution between both the cerium and lanthanum oxides and the cerium and cobalt/nickel oxides. As was mentioned, the calcination

Table 1
Chemical composition and textural properties of the prepared catalysts.

Catalysts	Co (wt%)	Ni (wt%)	La (wt%)	N_2 physisorption			H_2 chemisorption	
				D_p (nm)	V_p (mL/g)	S_{BET} (m^2/g)	S_M ($\text{m}^2/\text{g}_{\text{cat}}$)	Dispersion (%)
Co/CeO_2	7.7	–	–	16.2	0.15	34.2	2.7	5.2
$\text{Co-0.1La}/\text{CeO}_2$	7.6	–	2.0	16.0	0.17	38.9	4.8	9.2
Ni/CeO_2	–	9.1	–	13.9	0.16	39.8	4.0	6.7
$\text{Ni-0.1La}/\text{CeO}_2$	–	9.2	2.1	15.2	0.18	42.0	5.6	9.1

Fig. 1. STEM-EDS micrographs of (a) Co/CeO₂, (b) Co-0.1La/CeO₂, (c) Ni/CeO₂ and (d) Ni-0.1La/CeO₂ catalysts.

temperature of the catalyst was 650 °C since lower temperature operation could result in incomplete decomposition of La(NO₃)₃ × 6H₂O salt. However, such high temperature operation can cause aggregation of metal crystallites. Indeed, both Co₃O₄ and NiO crystallites of Co/CeO₂ and Ni/CeO₂ catalysts described in this work after calcination of their precursors at 650 °C are three (Co₃O₄) or even four times (NiO) larger than those obtained in the case of Co/CeO₂ and Ni/CeO₂ catalysts which were prepared in the same way but thermally treated at lower temperature of 500 °C and described in our previous work [38]. The calcination temperature, however, does not influence on CeO₂ crystallites size. The XRD

patterns of the reduced catalysts (Fig. 2a–d (B)) reveal the presence of CeO₂ phase without significant changes compared to the calcined samples (Fig. 2a–d (A)). Moreover, diffraction peaks for Co₃O₄ or NiO phases are not detected whereas that corresponding to a face-centered cubic structure of metallic cobalt [39] and nickel [40] at $2\theta = 44.2^\circ$ and 51.5° and $2\theta = 44.8^\circ$ and 52.2° for cobalt- and nickel based catalysts, respectively are observed. It confirms that Co₃O₄/NiO phases are completely converted into metallic cobalt/metallic nickel during reduction with hydrogen at 600 °C (see Supporting Information, Fig. S1). The intensities of the reflections corresponding to metallic cobalt/nickel on the catalyst promoted with La₂O₃ are slightly weaker than those on the other two catalysts which suggests that the crystallites of metallic cobalt/nickel in the case of Co-0.1La/CeO₂ and Ni-0.1La/CeO₂ catalysts are smaller than those on the Co/CeO₂ and Ni/CeO₂ ones and the dispersion of the former is better than that of the latter [41] which is consistent with hydrogen chemisorption results (Table 1). Moreover, the quantitative estimation of the crystallite sizes of the metallic cobalt/metallic nickel phases by applying the Scherrer equation (Table 2) confirms that their particles are smaller in comparison with the size of Co₃O₄/NiO crystallites. Whereas CeO₂ crystallite size remains almost unchanged for all catalysts after reduction in comparison with crystallite size of calcined samples (Table 2).

In order to study the reduction properties of the prepared catalysts, the H₂-TPR experiment was conducted and H₂-TPR profiles of Co/CeO₂, Co-0.1La/CeO₂, Ni/CeO₂, Ni-0.1La/CeO₂ catalysts and pure CeO₂ and La₂O₃/CeO₂ samples are presented in Fig. 3. For the cobalt-based catalysts, there are four well-defined reduction peaks. The peak at 100 °C is attributed to the reduction of the surface oxygen species [42,43] whereas the next three peaks correspond to stepwise reduction of Co₃O₄ to metallic cobalt. The first peak centered at 270 °C (Co/CeO₂) and 280 °C (Co-0.1La/CeO₂) is assigned to Co₃O₄ reduction to CoO [5,15,22,29] and the both next peaks are attributed to reduction of cobalt oxide species, with different extent of interaction with the support, to metallic cobalt. The maximum of hydrogen consumption at 320 °C results from reduction Co₃O₄ [43] or CoO [29,44,45] that weakly interacts with CeO₂ support whereas the next reduction peak at 490 °C (Co/CeO₂) and 500 °C (Co-0.1La/CeO₂) is related to the reduction of cobalt oxide species which strongly interacts with ceria [29,43–45]. It is interesting to find that the hydrogen consumption corresponding to peak at 320 °C is much lower for cobalt-based catalyst promoted with La₂O₃ (Table 3). But contrary dependence is observed in the case hydrogen consumption corresponding to the next peak which is much higher for Co-0.1La/CeO₂ compared with Co/CeO₂ catalyst (Table 3). Moreover, the reduction temperature of this peak shifts to higher temperature by ~10 °C upon La₂O₃ addition. These results suggest that in the presence of small amount of La₂O₃ promoter, there is better dispersion of cobalt active phase improving the strength metal-support interaction which is in the great accordance with results obtained from hydrogen chemisorption (Table 1) and XRD methods (Figs. 2 and S1, Table 2) [29,43–45]. Carvalho et al. [15], on the other hand, observed that all peaks in TPR profiles of Co₃O₄/La₂O₃/CeO₂ catalysts related to cobalt reduction shifted to lower temperature because of the La₂O₃ presence which was explained by facilitation of the reduction of cobalt oxide species by the oxygen vacancies from the Ce(La)O_x solid solution. A quantitative estimation of the hydrogen consumption attributed to reduction of cobalt oxide species indicates that the amount of hydrogen consumed greatly exceeds that required for the reduction of Co₃O₄ to metallic cobalt (Table 3). It allows to assumed that the extra hydrogen consumed is used for CeO₂ reduction [46]. According to the literature [29,43], the peak located at ~490 °C (500 °C) in the H₂-TPR profiles of Co/CeO₂ and Co-0.1La/CeO₂ catalysts corresponding to the cobalt oxide reduction could be

Fig. 2. Diffraction patterns of (a) Co/CeO₂, (b) Co-0.1La/CeO₂, (c) Ni/CeO₂ and (d) Ni-0.1La/CeO₂ catalysts. (A) after calcination in air at 650 °C, (B) after reduction with hydrogen at 600 °C and (C) after SRE reaction at 420 °C.

Table 2

Average crystallites size and lattice parameter of prepared catalysts.

Catalysts	XRD						
	Before reduction			After reduction		After SRE	
	Lattice parameter (nm)	d_{CeO_2} (nm)	$d_{\text{Co}_3\text{O}_4}/>\text{NiO}$ (nm)	d_{CeO_2} (nm)	$d_{\text{Co/Ni}}$ (nm)	d_{CeO_2} (nm)	$d_{\text{Co/Ni}}$ (nm)
Co/CeO ₂	5.411	23.7	22.0	23.4	14.0	25.9	–
Co-0.1La/CeO ₂	5.410	23.2	12.1	22.3	8.6	23.3	–
Ni/CeO ₂	5.411	23.4	16.0	23.4	12.3	25.1	–
Ni-0.1La/CeO ₂	5.411	23.3	9.2	22.2	8.6	23.5	–

overlapped with that of the reduction of surface ceria. In the case of nickel-based catalysts, small peaks below 260 °C could be ascribed to reduction of surface oxygen species [47–49]. Whereas a major

reduction peak is evidently observed for both samples in the temperature range of 260–420 °C and it can be attributed to the reduction of NiO into metallic nickel and partial reduction of the

Fig. 3. Temperature-programmed reduction profiles of CeO_2 , $\text{La}_2\text{O}_3/\text{CeO}_2$, Co/CeO_2 , $\text{Co-0.1La}/\text{CeO}_2$, Ni/CeO_2 and $\text{Ni-0.1La}/\text{CeO}_2$ samples.

surface ceria forming nonstoichiometric cerium oxides (CeO_x) [28,47–50]. These results indicate that NiO is reduced to metallic nickel completely far below temperature of reduction, i.e. 600 °C which is also confirmed by value of the experimental consumption of hydrogen calculated by integrating H_2 -TPR profiles (Table 3). As can be seen in Table 3, both nickel-based catalysts presented reduction degrees slightly above 100%, which can be associated with a partial reduction of support, forming suboxide species [28]. However, the comparison of values of reduction degree obtained for cobalt- and nickel-based catalysts clearly indicates that a higher reducibility of surface-capping oxygen of ceria because of probably higher promotion of the hydrogen spillover effect [51] is demonstrated by the samples with cobalt active phase. Moreover, for lanthanum promoted nickel-based catalyst, the major peak for consumption of hydrogen is shifted to higher temperature for ~20 °C compared to Ni/CeO_2 sample which suggests that NiO remains in more intimate contact with ceria in the case of $\text{Ni-0.1La}/\text{CeO}_2$ catalyst. This result is in a good accordance with those obtained by Ref. [41] who suggested that La_2O_3 is a kind of structural promoter, which can inhibit the aggregation of nickel particles

during reduction by hydrogen and is consistent with our XRD results (Figs. 2 and S1). In the case of $\text{Co-0.1La}/\text{CeO}_2$ and $\text{Ni-0.1La}/\text{CeO}_2$ catalysts, any peaks related to the direct reduction of lanthanum species are not observed. Moreover, the H_2 -TPR profiles of CeO_2 and $\text{La}_2\text{O}_3/\text{CeO}_2$ samples (Fig. 3) are almost identical and a quantitative estimation of the temperature signals indicates that amount of hydrogen consumed below 600 °C (Table 3) is the same for both CeO_2 and $\text{La}_2\text{O}_3/\text{CeO}_2$ samples, reaching value of 0.21 mmol/g. It suggests that all hydrogen consumed is used only for ceria reduction while lanthanum remains in its oxide form. Defects created during the incorporation of La^{3+} can lead to ease of formation of labile oxygen vacancies, connected to this relatively high mobility of bulk oxygen species within the lattice cell thereby enhancement in the ceria reducibility [52]. However, since both CeO_2 and $\text{La}_2\text{O}_3/\text{CeO}_2$ samples exhibit the same reactivity of lattice oxygen (the same values of hydrogen consumption), it can be excluded formation of solid solution as a result of the diffusion of La^{3+} into ceria lattice which is in good accordance with results obtained by XRD method. For both pure CeO_2 and $\text{La}_2\text{O}_3/\text{CeO}_2$ samples, three peaks are observed at around 230 °C, 420 °C and above 600 °C characteristic of reduction of the surface oxygen species, the outer layers of Ce^{4+} and bulk Ce^{4+} , respectively [46]. Also the peak observed above 600 °C in case of both cobalt- and nickel-based catalysts can be attributed to the partial reduction of bulk CeO_2 to Ce_2O_3 [5,16,22,27,29].

In order to evaluate the oxygen storage capacity of Co/CeO_2 , $\text{Co-0.1La}/\text{CeO}_2$, Ni/CeO_2 and $\text{Ni-0.1La}/\text{CeO}_2$ catalysts, O_2 -TPO analysis was conducted and the results are shown in Fig. 4. The obtained results cannot be attributed to only the oxidation of Ce^{3+} in oxygen vacancies, because oxidation of metallic cobalt or nickel in the studied range of temperature from RT to 600 °C cannot be excluded. Moreover, our previous studies [38] indicate that oxygen consumption in this temperature range observed for Co/CeO_2 , and Ni/CeO_2 materials result only from oxidation of cobalt or nickel species. However, these studies show that OSC values are slightly higher for both cobalt- and nickel-based catalyst without La_2O_3 addition. According to Kolli et al. [53], it can be due to lack of any oxygen storage capacity by La_2O_3 component. The La_2O_3 promoter could have been deposited on oxygen vacancies (regions where CeO_x is in contact with the metal) on the catalyst and therefore, partially inhibited the oxygen storage or release processes.

3.2. Influence of La_2O_3 promoter and active metal phase on catalytic performance of cobalt- and nickel-based catalysts in the steam reforming of ethanol

To investigate the catalytic activity of the lanthanum-promoted cobalt- and nickel-based catalysts in comparison with those catalysts without La_2O_3 addition in the SRE reaction, their catalytic

Table 3
Hydrogen consumption from H_2 -TPR results.

Catalysts	H ₂ consumption values (mmol/g)				Experimental for Co_3O_4 reduction ^a	Theoretical for Co_3O_4 reduction
	T ₁ (20–140 °C)	T ₂ (140–380 °C)	T ₃ (380–600 °C)	T ₃ (380–600 °C)		
Co/CeO_2	0.15	0.44	0.62	0.83	2.04	1.31
$\text{Co-0.1La}/\text{CeO}_2$	0.10	0.41	0.36	1.07	1.94	1.29
	T ₁ (20–260 °C)		T ₂ (260–600 °C)		Experimental for NiO reduction ^a	Theoretical for NiO reduction
Ni/CeO_2	0.18	1.53	1.71	1.55		
$\text{Ni-0.1La}/\text{CeO}_2$	0.14	1.55	1.69	1.57		
	H ₂ consumption values (mmol/g) (20–600 °C)					
$\text{La}_2\text{O}_3/\text{CeO}_2$	0.21					
CeO_2	0.21					

^a Obtained by integration of the reduction profile up to 600 °C.

Fig. 4. Oxygen consumption during O₂-TPO over Co/CeO₂, Co-0.1La/CeO₂, Ni/CeO₂ and Ni-0.1La/CeO₂ catalysts.

performance was evaluated at a high space velocity of 60000 mL/g_{cat} h, and the results are shown in Fig. 5. The catalytic activity of Co-0.1La/CeO₂ and Ni-0.1La/CeO₂ catalysts under SRE conditions at 420 °C after 21 h is higher than that for samples unpromoted with La₂O₃ probably due to larger active metal surface area of the catalysts with promoter (Table 1) [54]. The greater cobalt/nickel species dispersion means more active size available to react [5]. Similarly, Dan et al. [19] observed that addition of 6% of La₂O₃ to γ-alumina and zirconia significantly increase of ethanol conversion over obtained Ni/La₂O₃-Al₂O₃ and Ni/La₂O₃-ZrO₂ attributing it the improvement of nickel species dispersion. Moreover, both nickel-based catalysts promoted and unpromoted with La₂O₃ exhibit much higher ethanol conversion than both cobalt-based samples which is not surprising taking into account results obtained by Zhao et al. [4] and Zhang et al. [55]. After 21 h of SRE reaction, conversion of ethanol over Ni-0.1La/CeO₂ catalyst is still close to 100% but decrease to ~90% over Ni/CeO₂ catalyst. Whereas in the presence of Co/CeO₂ and Co-0.1La/CeO₂ samples ethanol is only 45 and 60% converted, respectively. Because of strong capacity of nickel active phase for breaking of C–C bond in ethanol, only traceable amount of acetaldehyde and no other C₂ or C₃ products were detected after 21 h of SRE reaction for Ni/CeO₂ and Ni-0.1La/CeO₂ catalysts. Slightly less of acetaldehyde, however, is produced in the presence of the sample with La₂O₃ promoter which can be attributed to higher nickel phase dispersion of Ni-0.1La/CeO₂ catalysts leading to higher nickel surface area for breaking C–C bond [7]. Compared to nickel-based samples, Co/CeO₂ and Co-0.1La/CeO₂ catalysts show much higher selectivity to C₂ and C₃ by-products after 21 h of SRE reaction. Because amounts of these by-products in the outlet at the beginning of the SRE reaction was lower, their higher production after 21 h of process confirms cobalt-based catalysts deactivation as result of decrease of the number of cobalt active sites for C–C bond breakage [7]. Although ethylene is produced at a rather trace level (<0.5%), acetaldehyde and acetone formation over Co/CeO₂ and Co-0.1La/CeO₂ samples is definitely high. The presence of these products suggests the participation of dehydrogenation (reaction 1) and dehydration (reaction 2) of ethanol and aldol condensation of acetaldehyde (reaction 3) processes:

More acetaldehyde by around 10% is formed in the presence of Co-0.1La/CeO₂ catalyst. Whereas acetone production is higher by around 10% over Co/CeO₂ sample. These results suggest that smaller amount of acetaldehyde undergoes subsequent transformation to acetone in the presence of La₂O₃ promoter which means that its addition to Co/CeO₂ catalyst allows to limit aldol condensation of acetaldehyde. Taking into account that acetone is very undesirable by-product because can polymerize to produce carbon which would cause catalyst deactivation [12,56], the influence of La₂O₃ promoter on selectivity of SRE reaction over Co/CeO₂ catalyst is very advantageous. Also ethylene tends to form coke through polymerization-carbon chain growth reactions [4]. Therefore, similarly to acetone, even the trace amounts of this product detected among the products of SRE reactions are highly undesirable. As can be seen in Fig. 4, the selectivity to ethylene decreases over cobalt-based catalyst containing La₂O₃ promoter which suggests that in its presence, dehydration of ethanol (reaction 1) occurs to a lesser extent. This result differs from that obtained by Abd El-Hafiz and Ebiad [14] who indicated that compared to Co/CeO₂, Co/CeO₂-La₂O₃ catalysts favored dehydration route. On the other hand, the formation of methane is favored under SRE conditions over both nickel-based catalysts (Fig. 4) and presence of this product could also lead to carbon formation due to the possible reaction of methane decomposition (reaction 4).

As it was mentioned both Ni/CeO₂ and Ni-0.1La/CeO₂ catalysts indicate high selectivity towards methane formation which slightly decreases from 37% to 33% during 21 h of SRE reaction. Whereas cobalt-based catalysts exhibit much lower formation of this product which changes from ~6% to ~8% for Co/CeO₂ and Co-0.1La/CeO₂ catalysts, respectively at the beginning of the SRE reaction to ~3% for both samples after 21 h of process time. These results indicate that presence of La₂O₃ promoter does not influence on methane production over both Co/CeO₂ and Ni/CeO₂ catalysts. Methane formation could be attributed to direct ethanol or acetaldehyde decomposition (reaction 5 and 6) as well as to methanation reactions (reactions 7 and 8):

According to Zhang et al. [55], strong capacity of nickel species for breaking C–C bond in ethanol and only traceable amounts of acetaldehyde and acetone suggest that the main reaction over Ni/CeO₂ catalyst is ethanol decomposition to methane (reaction 5). On the other hand, it is also shared opinion that the dehydrogenation of ethanol to acetaldehyde (reaction 4), produced on nickel species can be considered the first crucial step and that methane production is subsequent to acetaldehyde decomposition (reaction 6) [6,57]. Because the formation of acetaldehyde is significantly inhibited in the presence of Ni/CeO₂ and Ni-0.1La/CeO₂ catalysts, it can suggest that adsorbed acetaldehyde decomposes generating

Fig. 5. Catalytic performance of Co/CeO₂, Co-0.1La/CeO₂, Ni/CeO₂ and Ni-0.1La/CeO₂ catalysts (H₂O/EtOH = 12/1, GHSV = 60000 mL/g h, TOS = 21 h) in the ethanol steam reforming at 420 °C.

methane and carbon monoxide. The low amount of carbon monoxide among the products obtained over nickel-based catalysts (<4%), on the other hand, can also indicate that nickel species display a high activity for the methanation (reaction 7) as was suggested by Manfro et al. [29] and Davidson et al. [58]. Because production of carbon monoxide in the presence of cobalt-based catalysts is much higher (~12% at the beginning of SRE reaction) than methane, the methanation (reaction 7) rather does not occur. But these results suggest that these catalysts promote the steam reforming of methane (reaction 9) as it was proposed by Carvalho et al. [15] for $\text{Co}_3\text{O}_4/\text{CeO}_2$, $\text{Co}_3\text{O}_4/\text{La}_2\text{O}_3$ and $\text{Co}_3\text{O}_4/\text{CeO}_2/\text{La}_2\text{O}_3$ catalysts.

In the case of cobalt-based samples, the selectivity to carbon monoxide decreases during the SRE reaction but more of this product is formed over the catalyst promoted with La_2O_3 . It is probably connected with higher activity of this sample. Because of its slower deactivation, it is longer capable of breaking of C–C bond and formation of this C1 product than unpromoted with La_2O_3 catalyst. Both Co/CeO_2 and $\text{Co-0.1La}/\text{CeO}_2$ catalysts, however, undergo deactivation during the SRE reaction which explains the decrease of carbon monoxide production to from 12% to 6% and 8%, respectively and increase contribution of C2 and C3 products. On the other hand, the selectivity to carbon monoxide over nickel-based catalysts increases during SRE reaction despite their insignificant deactivation. The small amount of acetaldehyde and lack of any other C2 and C3 products indicates that a large number of active nickel sites of these catalysts are still available to react in contrast to much more deactivated cobalt active phase of the cobalt-based samples. The insignificant increase of carbon monoxide amount in the presence of nickel-based catalysts from 1.5% to 2.5% and 3.5% for Ni/CeO_2 and $\text{Ni-0.1La}/\text{CeO}_2$ catalysts, respectively with simultaneous decrease of methane production results from limitation of activity of these catalysts toward methanation (reaction 7) with the increase in the SRE reaction time. Also studies of Lu et al. [33] indicated an influence of La_2O_3 promoter on nickel-based catalyst selectivity to carbon monoxide in the methanol steam reforming, showing lower selectivity to carbon monoxide over $\text{La-Ni}/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ compared with $\text{Ni}/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ catalyst. Since carbon monoxide is a poison of platinum anodes in the low-temperature fuel cells, suppression or even total elimination of its formation is a very important issue [29,59]. Moreover, carbon monoxide disproportionation (Boudouard reaction, reaction 10) can lead to carbon formation:

Because all studied cobalt- and nickel-based catalysts exhibit lower formation of carbon monoxide in comparison with carbon dioxide formation, it can indicate that carbon monoxide is converted into carbon dioxide by the Boudouard reaction (reaction 10). On the other hand, Marcos et al. [5] suggested that water gas shift reaction, WGS, (reaction 11) was favored by ceria supported catalysts.

Also according to Zhang et al. [55] the much lower concentrations of carbon monoxide in the outlet stream could be ascribed to the efficient WGS reaction (reaction 11) promoted by the high OH group surface mobility of ceria support. The significant decrease of selectivity to carbon dioxide in the first hours of the SRE reaction from ~40% to 64% for Co/CeO_2 and $\text{Co-0.1La}/\text{CeO}_2$ catalysts,

respectively to ~32% for both samples results from decrease of the number of active cobalt sites because of their deactivation. Whereas the production of carbon dioxide over Ni/CeO_2 and $\text{Ni-0.1La}/\text{CeO}_2$ remains relatively constant until the end of the catalytic test, maintaining the level of 62% and 64% respectively. Also selectivity to the most desirable product of SRE reaction, i.e. hydrogen does not change in the presence of both nickel-based catalysts with the increase of the process time and it equals to ~72% for both samples. Whereas hydrogen formation over Co/CeO_2 and $\text{Co-0.1La}/\text{CeO}_2$ catalysts decreases from 77% to 88%, respectively in the first hours of the SRE reaction to ~70% for both samples which, similarly to observed decrease of C1 products, is connected with catalysts deactivation.

It could be concluded that La_2O_3 promoter improves the activity and stability of Co/CeO_2 and Ni/CeO_2 catalysts as the result of the cobalt/nickel dispersion improvement. Moreover, this promoter influence on the amount of carbon monoxide and acetaldehyde produced in the presence of nickel-based catalyst and carbon monoxide, acetaldehyde, acetone and ethylene over cobalt-based sample after 21 h of SRE reaction. In the case of other products, it is not observed any significant influence of La_2O_3 addition after this time. However, much more hydrogen and carbon dioxide are produced at the initial stage of process in the presence of $\text{Co-0.1La}/\text{CeO}_2$ catalyst in comparison with the Co/CeO_2 sample. What is more, nickel as an active phase is much more active for breaking C–C bond than cobalt. Therefore, both nickel-based catalysts almost do not generate C2 products whereas for cobalt-based samples, C2 and C3 products in significant amounts are detected in the SRE reaction outlet.

To estimate the influence of La_2O_3 promoter on intrinsic catalytic activity of cobalt and nickel active sites, TOF values were calculated and they were as follows 0.030 s^{-1} , 0.017 s^{-1} , 0.020 s^{-1} and 0.011 s^{-1} for Co/CeO_2 , $\text{Co-0.1La}/\text{CeO}_2$, Ni/CeO_2 and $\text{Ni-0.1La}/\text{CeO}_2$ catalyst, respectively. These results clearly demonstrates that the addition of La_2O_3 promoter does not improve intrinsic catalytic activity of cobalt/nickel sites. On the other hand, these results can suggest that it is a relationship between cobalt/nickel crystallite size and the intrinsic activity. Whereas edge/corner sites are proposed as active sites for C–C cleavage [60], ethanol

Fig. 6. Carbon formation rate over Co/CeO_2 , $\text{Co-0.1La}/\text{CeO}_2$, Ni/CeO_2 and $\text{Ni-0.1La}/\text{CeO}_2$ catalysts.

dehydrogenation to acetaldehyde occurs preferably on terrace sites [61]. Since the TOF values were measured at low conversion, the dehydrogenation of ethanol was the initial step of ethanol reformation over cobalt- and nickel-based catalysts. Because the fraction of terrace sites increase with the increase in the crystallite size, the TOF values correspond to rate of the ethanol dehydrogenation increase with the increase in cobalt or nickel crystallite size. Therefore, the higher values of TOF were obtained for cobalt- or nickel based catalysts which were unpromoted with La_2O_3 promoter because these catalysts exhibited higher size of metal crystallites (Table 2).

3.3. Characterization of spent catalysts

Three major categories of deactivation mechanism are known and they are catalyst sintering, poisoning and carbon formation. They can occur either individually or in combination, but the net effect is always the removal of active sites from the catalyst surface. Carbon deposition has been reported to be the major deactivation mechanism of SRE process [1].

To investigate the formation of carbonaceous residues, the cobalt- and nickel based catalysts after SRE reaction at 420 °C were subjected to thermogravimetric analysis. The values of carbon formation rate were calculated considering the amount of carbon formed during 21 h of SRE reactions over Co/CeO₂, Co-0.1La/CeO₂, Ni/CeO₂ and Ni-0.1La/CeO₂ catalysts and obtained results are presented in Fig. 6. Compared to cobalt based-samples, the carbon formation rate over nickel-based catalysts was markedly higher. Whereas the carbon was formed on the surface of Co/CeO₂, Co-0.1La/CeO₂, samples with the rate of 6.6 mg/g h and 1.8 mg/g h, values of carbon rate formation over Ni/CeO₂ and Ni-0.1La/CeO₂ catalysts were calculated as equal to 365.9 mg/g h and 202.8 mg/g h, respectively. The results obtained by thermogravimetric method do not allow to explain the faster deactivation of cobalt-based than nickel-based catalysts under SRE conditions (Fig. 5). What is more, very high values of carbon formation rate obtained for Ni/CeO₂ and Ni-0.1La/CeO₂ catalysts suggest that these samples should deactivate much faster than cobalt-based ones. Although the results concerning deactivation rate (Fig. 5) and carbon formation rate (Fig. 6) depending on metal active phase are contrary, in the case of effect of La_2O_3 promoter on resistance to deactivation of cobalt- and nickel based catalysts, the results obtained by thermogravimetric method (Fig. 6) and catalytic experiment (Fig. 5) are in a good agreement. The less carbon formation rates over catalysts promoted with La_2O_3 explains their better performance and stability in SRE reaction (Fig. 4). Also Osorio-Vargas et al. [7] observed that the presence of La_2O_3 promoter markedly suppresses the carbon formation on catalyst surface during the SRE suggesting that La_2O_3 acts as an intermediate, promoting the reaction between the carbon species and carbon dioxide. La_2O_3 reacts with carbon dioxide to form $\text{La}_2\text{O}_2\text{CO}_3$ (reaction 12) which eliminates carbon deposited through the reaction 13 [4,7].

On the other hand, it is well known that the carbon formation over metallic cobalt/nickel particles is significantly affected by their crystallites size. The cobalt or nickel particles of larger size favors carbon deposition whereas the initiation step for carbon formation over metal is more difficult for smaller crystallites [8,62,63]. Because introduction of La_2O_3 promoter led to obtain smaller metallic cobalt/nickel crystallites size during reduction treatment (Fig. 2a–d (B)) the lowest carbon formation observed on the surface

Co-0.1La/CeO₂ and Ni-0.1La/CeO₂ catalysts could be attributed to better dispersion of metal active phase.

The XRD patterns of the Ni/CeO₂ and Ni-0.1La/CeO₂ catalysts after SRE reaction at 420 °C presented in Fig. 2c and d (C) confirms the presence of carbon on the surface nickel-based catalysts because reflection at $2\theta = 26^\circ$ corresponded to graphite-type carbon are observed [5,15]. The stronger intensity of this reflection in the XRD pattern of Ni/CeO₂ sample indicates larger carbon accumulation. The lack of this characteristic line in XRD patterns of cobalt-based catalysts in Fig. 2a and b (C) results probably from low amount of carbon on the surface of these catalysts which is not detected by XRD method [29]. The results obtained for both cobalt- and nickel based samples are in good accordance with results obtained by thermogravimetric method. Although the reflection at $2\theta = 26^\circ$ can be attributed to $\text{La}_2\text{O}_2\text{CO}_3$, it is assigned to graphitic carbon because of its presence in XRD pattern of both nickel-based catalysts, this containing La_2O_3 promoter and this without its addition (Fig. 2c and d (C)). Moreover, the one characteristic line of $\text{La}_2\text{O}_2\text{CO}_3$ ($2\theta = 44.6^\circ$) which overlaps with main line corresponding to metallic nickel is ascribed only to metallic nickel as can be seen in Fig. 2c and d (C). The presence of these reflection in XRD pattern of both Ni/CeO₂ and Ni-0.1La/CeO₂ catalysts excludes that it comes from $\text{La}_2\text{O}_2\text{CO}_3$. It could be concluded that there is no formation of the species $\text{La}_2\text{O}_2\text{CO}_3$ in the case neither Co-0.1La/CeO₂ nor Ni-0.1La/CeO₂ catalysts. Marcos et al. [5] suggested that a low content of La_2O_3 could be insufficient to react with a carbon dioxide. Therefore, the XRD results indicates that the lower coke production observed for Co-0.1La/CeO₂ and Ni-0.1La/CeO₂ samples in comparison with catalysts without La_2O_3 promoter results from the smaller particles size of nickel/cobalt crystallites of catalysts containing promoter. According to Silva et al. [60], the reduced amount of carbon deposition over cobalt-based catalysts is ascribed to a lower fraction of terrace atoms, proposed to be responsible for initiation of carbon deposition on catalysts with large (>10 nm) cobalt particles. Whereas small nickel crystallites size results in a large saturation concentration leading to a low driving force for carbon diffusion and hence a lower coking rate [64]. Moreover, the small particle size of active phase results in enhanced metal-support interactions which not only favors the of C–C, C–H and O–H bonds cleavage to improve catalytic activity but also makes the cleavage of C–O bonds more difficult to prevent carbon deposition by inhibiting the Boudouard reaction (reaction 10) during SRE [2,65]. None of the used cobalt-based catalysts shows reflections corresponding to metallic cobalt (Fig. 2a and b (C)). Whereas both used nickel-based samples exhibits diffraction lines corresponding to the metallic nickel at $2\theta = 44.8^\circ$ (Fig. 2c and d (C)) but with much lower intensity compared to catalysts after reduction (Fig. 2c and d (B)). It was even impossible quantitative estimation of crystallites size of metallic nickel in the used in SRE samples by applying Scherer equation (Table 2). These results obtained for both cobalt- and nickel-based catalysts suggest defragmentation of cobalt/nickel particles by carbonaceous deposits [25].

Elemental mapping was also performed for the spent Co/CeO₂, Co-0.1La/CeO₂, Ni/CeO₂ and Ni-0.1La/CeO₂ catalysts to obtain information about the spatial distribution of the different catalysts components after SRE reaction (see Supporting Information, Figs. S2a–d). STEM-EDS maps of all studied catalysts confirm the formation of carbon under the SRE conditions. In the case of Co-0.1La/CeO₂ and Ni-0.1La/CeO₂ catalysts (Figs. S2b and d), the distribution of cobalt/nickel and cerium elements reveal that cobalt or nickel active phase remains distributed mainly on the ceria support. Whereas the STEM-EDS maps of Co/CeO₂ and Ni/CeO₂ catalysts (Figs. S2a and c) show areas that cobalt or nickel active phase is in contact with surface of ceria but it is also observed that part of cobalt/nickel species is isolated from ceria support. According to

Fig. 7. TEM images of a) Co/CeO₂, (b) Co-0.1La/CeO₂, (c) Ni/CeO₂ and (d) Ni-0.1La/CeO₂ catalysts after 21 h of the SRE process (H₂O/EtOH = 12/1, T = 420 °C).

Słowik [25], it suggest that part of the cobalt/nickel active phase is pushed from the support by the carbon deposits.

The morphology of the spent Co/CeO₂, Co-0.1La/CeO₂, Ni/CeO₂ and Ni-0.1La/CeO₂ catalysts after SRE reaction was studied by means of SEM method (see Supporting Information, Figs. S3a–d). Not observable carbon deposits is appeared in the SEM images of Co-0.1La/CeO₂ catalyst (Fig. S3b) because it is formed on the surface of this sample in a small amount. An inconsiderable quantity of short filamentous carbon is observed on the surface of the Co/CeO₂ sample (Fig. S3a). Whereas SEM images of both nickel-based catalysts (Figs. S3c and d) confirm the coverage of their surface by the considerable amount of long filamentous carbon structures. All these results are in agreement with those obtained by the thermogravimetric method.

TEM images, presented in Fig. 7a–d, reveal that cobalt and nickel used as the active phase of ceria supported catalysts for SRE reaction lead to carbon deposits with different degree of its graphitization. Taking into account only the degree of graphitization of carbon deposit formed on the surface of catalyst, a deactivating effect of the carbon on the catalyst activity and stability increased in the following order: from disordered (amorphous) carbons, to less ordered (turbostratic) carbons and to highly ordered carbons such as graphite. Amorphous carbon, reported to be very active, can easily be removed from the catalyst surface at low temperatures and may not cause deactivation of the catalyst. While graphitic carbon requires higher

temperatures to oxidize and could limit the activity of the catalysts acting like a shell on the catalyst and completely covering the metal active sites layer by layer [66,67]. Moreover, based on the mechanism of carbon formation, non-filamentous (encapsulating) and filamentous carbon are the most important types of carbon formed. The carbon filamentous do not deactivate the catalyst as encapsulating carbon does. Carbon filamentous allow to metallic cobalt to remain exposed to the reactants for a longer period of time, causing the catalyst remain active throughout the reaction, which explains the good performance and non-deactivation, despite the presence of carbon. The encapsulating carbon deactivates the catalyst by decreasing the total number of active sites [5,68].

A generally accepted mechanism of filament growth consists of the formation of carbon species on the surface of the metals, dissolution in the metal, diffusion through the metal and precipitation from the metal at a point on the surface, resulting in the formation of the filament body, not necessary causing a loss of intrinsic catalysts activity unless carbon filaments are formed in sufficient quantities to cause plugging of the pores. The filament growth can be, however, ceased when the metal particle is encapsulated by the formation of carbon deposit [67,69].

In the case of cobalt-based catalysts (Fig. 7a and b), the carbon deposited is a combination of filamentous carbon and non-filamentous (encapsulating) carbon. The carbon filamentous are

Fig. 8. Stability tests of Co-0.1La/CeO₂ catalyst at temperature of (a) 460 °C and (b) 500 °C and Ni-0.1La/CeO₂ catalyst at temperature of (a) 460 °C under the steam reforming conditions (H₂O/EtOH = 12/1, GHSV = 60000 mL/g h, TOS = 21 h).

Table 4
Catalytic results in SRE reaction over cobalt- and nickel-based catalysts promoted with lanthanum.

Catalysts	Operating conditions in SRE	Ethanol conversion	Main products	Ref.
Co/CeO ₂ -La ₂ O ₃ Co content ~10 wt% Ce/Ce molar ratio = 4 Ce/La molar ratio = 0.2	Reaction temperature = 500 °C; Catalyst weight = 500 mg; H ₂ O/EtOH molar ratio = 10/1; H ₂ O/EtOH mixture flow rate = 0.2 ml/min N ₂ flow rate = 40 ml/min	100%; TOS = 15h	Selectivity: H ₂ : 66%, CO: ~25%, CO ₂ : ~2%, CH ₄ : 2%.	[14]
Co ₃ O ₄ /La ₂ O ₃ /CeO ₂ , Co content ~20 wt% CeO ₂ /La ₂ O ₃ molar ratio = 88/12	Reaction temperature = 500 °C; Catalyst weight = 150 mg; H ₂ O/EtOH molar ratio = 3/1; H ₂ O/EtOH mixture flow rate = 0.04 ml/min	97%; TOS = 20h	Selectivity in mol/mol _{EtOH} : H ₂ : 3, CO: 0.25, CO ₂ : 1, CH ₄ : 0.25%; C ₂ H ₄ :0.06%	[15]
Co-0.1La/CeO ₂	Reaction temperature = 500 °C; Catalyst weight = 100 mg; H ₂ O/EtOH molar ratio = 12/1; H ₂ O/EtOH mixture flow rate = 100 ml/min (without any dilution with inert gas) GHSV = 60000 ml/g h	100%; TOS = 21h	Selectivity: H ₂ : 94%, CO: 10%, CO ₂ : 88%, CH ₃ CHO: 0.6%, CH ₄ : 10%.	This work
Ni-La-Ce-I Ni content ~12 wt%	Reaction temperature = 650 °C; Catalyst weight = 100 mg; H ₂ O/EtOH molar ratio = 3/1; H ₂ O/EtOH mixture flow rate = 1.2 ml/min N ₂ flow rate = 60 ml/min GHSV = 180000 ml/g h	90%; TOS = 8h	Selectivity: H ₂ : 60%, CO: 25%, CO ₂ : 9%, CH ₃ CHO: 5%, CH ₄ : 5%.	[12]
Ni-La-Ce-C Ni content ~12 wt%	Reaction temperature = 650 °C; Catalyst weight = 100 mg; H ₂ O/EtOH molar ratio = 3/1; H ₂ O/EtOH mixture flow rate = 1.2 ml/min N ₂ flow rate = 60 ml/min GHSV = 180000 ml/g h	100%; TOS = 8h	Selectivity: H ₂ : 60%, CO: 25%, CO ₂ : 18%, CH ₄ : 2%.	[12]
Ni/La ₂ O ₃ -Al ₂ O ₃ ; Ni content ~10 wt% La ₂ O ₃ content ~15 wt%	Reaction temperature = 450 °C; Catalyst weight = 100 mg; H ₂ O/EtOH molar ratio = 3/1; H ₂ O/EtOH mixture flow rate = 0.09 ml/min Ar flow rate = 137 ml/min GHSV = 26000 h ⁻¹	89%; TOS = 24h	Selectivity: H ₂ : 58%, CO: 7%, CO ₂ : 19%, CH ₃ CHO: 0.67%, (CH ₃) ₂ CO: 0.13% CH ₄ : 14%; C ₂ H ₄ :0.92% C ₂ H ₆ :0.11%	[7]
Ni/La ₂ O ₃ -CeO ₂ -Al ₂ O ₃ ; Ni content ~10 wt% La ₂ O ₃ content ~15 wt% CeO ₂ content ~10 wt%	Reaction temperature = 450 °C; Catalyst weight = 100 mg; H ₂ O/EtOH molar ratio = 3/1; H ₂ O/EtOH mixture flow rate = 0.09 ml/min Ar flow rate = 137 ml/min GHSV = 26000 h ⁻¹	98%; TOS = 24h	Selectivity: H ₂ : 76%, CO: 9.9%, CO ₂ : 11%, CH ₃ CHO: 0.1%, CH ₄ : 8.9%; C ₂ H ₄ :0.15%	[7]
Ni/La ₂ O ₃ -Al ₂ O ₃ ; Ni content ~13.8 wt% La/Al molar ratio = 0.1	Reaction temperature = 450 °C; Catalyst weight = 100 mg; H ₂ O/EtOH molar ratio = 6/1; Ar flow rate = 40 ml/min GHSV = 23140 ml/g h	100%; TOS = 15h	H ₂ yield: 123.3% Selectivity CO: 8.9%, CO ₂ : 63.9%, CH ₄ : 27.2%.	[70]
Ni-0.1La/CeO ₂	Reaction temperature = 460 °C; Catalyst weight = 100 mg; H ₂ O/EtOH molar ratio = 12/1; H ₂ O/EtOH mixture flow rate = 100 ml/min (without any dilution with inert gas) GHSV = 60000 ml/g h	100%; TOS = 21h	Selectivity: H ₂ : 80%, CO: 3%, CO ₂ : 68%, CH ₄ : 30%.	This work

short because cobalt particles located on their tip were fast encapsulated under SRE conditions by carbon deposit what ceased the further growth of filaments. Moreover, there is observed the non-filamentous (encapsulating) carbon covering a surface of cobalt-based catalysts. The other phenomenon discovered by using TEM method concerns the degree of graphitization of cobalt-based catalysts. The carbon deposited all over the catalyst exhibits a highly ordered structure and graphitic character. A short length of carbon filamentous, non-filamentous (encapsulating) carbon covering the surface of cobalt-based catalysts and a high degree of carbon graphitization suggest that the deactivation rate of the cobalt-based catalysts was rather fast and is in good accordance with results obtained during the catalytic test (Fig. 5). Deactivation likely occurs because the active cobalt sites become increasingly encapsulated by graphitic carbon [65].

The complexity of the deactivation dynamics previously proved by Montero et al. [9], showing three different stages in the evolution with time on stream: (i) ascribed to the formation of filamentous carbon with little impact on the catalyst activity; ii) related to the graphitization of filamentous carbon which causes severe deactivation by encapsulating the metal active sites and formation of a highly-deactivating non-filamentous (encapsulating) carbon which starts to cover the catalyst surface; iii) slow deposition of a non-filamentous (encapsulating) carbon which covers almost completely the catalyst surface and its high graphitization. The TEM results obtained for cobalt-based catalyst in this work suggest that all stages of deactivation occurred during 20 h of SRE reaction at 420 °C over these samples causing their rapid deactivation. Although the formation of filamentous carbon is observed, fast deactivation of cobalt-based catalyst suggests

preferential formation of encapsulating carbon during the initial stages of the reaction. Carbon deposition is initially high and with time the rate of deposition decreases, because the majority of the metallic sites are becoming inactive because of their encapsulation.

In the case of nickel based catalysts, TEM images (Fig. 7c and d) shows that SRE at 420 °C reaction led to highly developed filamentous type carbon deposits on the catalyst surface. More abundant and longer carbon filaments with a less ordered structure, namely turbostratic character with respect to cobalt-based samples are formed on both nickel-based catalysts. The high amount of carbon formation and the low decrease in ethanol conversion (Fig. 5) is a strong indication of prevailing formation of filamentous carbon, and not encapsulating as it is confirmed by TEM images (Fig. 7c and d). The filamentous carbon has less incidence in catalyst deactivation since it does not block the active nickel sites. This fact explains the lower deactivation rate observed in the presence of nickel-based than cobalt-based catalysts (Fig. 5) despite the high amount of carbon deposited (Fig. 6). Moreover, although during 20 h of reaction carbon deposit formed over nickel-based catalysts undergoes gradual graphitization, it indicates much less graphitization degree than carbon deposited on the surface of cobalt-based catalysts and less tendency to wrap the nickel particles by carbon layers.

Although Charisiou et al. [70] indicate that the addition of La₂O₃ can lead to a less graphitic structure of deposited carbon, it was not confirmed by these studies. However, the influence of active metal phase on the graphitization degree of carbon under SRE conditions is affirmed. Nickel-based active phase prevents from gradual graphitization of carbon deposited to a larger extent than cobalt-based phase. Not only TEM images shows that the less ordered structure of carbon deposits are formed on the nickel-based catalysts rather than on these with cobalt active phase. The confirmation of these results are also TG curves obtained for spent catalyst (see Supporting Information, Fig. S4). The weight loss appears in the TG profile of cobalt-based catalysts at ~560 °C but lower temperature was necessary to remove the carbon deposits from the surface of the nickel-based samples. The shift of the temperature corresponding to combustion of carbon depositions toward a higher temperature results from the increase of degree graphitization. Therefore, TG analysis confirms that nickel-based catalysts exhibit less graphitization degree than carbon deposited on the surface of cobalt-based materials.

3.4. Stability test of Co-0.1La/CeO₂ and Ni-0.1La/CeO₂ at different temperatures

The performance of Co-0.1La/CeO₂ and Ni-0.1La/CeO₂ catalysts studied under SRE conditions was also evaluated in terms of ethanol conversion, product distributions and stability at 460 °C and 500 °C. Comparison of results of catalytic behavior of these catalysts at different temperatures in SRE process presented in Figs. 5 and 8a–c show that the increase of temperature from 420 °C to 500 °C for Co-0.1La/CeO₂ sample and from 420 °C to 460 °C for Ni-0.1La/CeO₂ influences the ethanol conversion. The higher temperature of SRE reaction is, the higher ethanol conversion is obtained after 21 h of SRE. In the case of nickel based samples, temperature of 460 °C is sufficient to obtain complete ethanol conversion during 21 h of SRE process without presence of any C₂ or C₃ products in the outlet (Fig. 8c). Hydrogen and C₁ products, i.e. carbon dioxide, methane and carbon monoxide, are the only products formed over Ni-0.1La/CeO₂ sample at 460 °C and the selectivity to them during 21 h of SRE reaction was kept at almost constant level of ~80%, 68%, 30%, and 3%, respectively. The products distribution suggests that the main reaction is ethanol decomposition to methane and carbon monoxide (reaction 5) because of the strong ability of nickel active phase for

breaking C–C bond in ethanol. Most of the produced carbon monoxide is converted into carbon dioxide through the WGS reaction (reaction 11), leading to very low concentration of undesirable carbon monoxide in the outlet [55]. Moreover, because of high activity of supported nickel catalysts in the methanation reactions of carbon monoxide and/or carbon dioxide (reactions 7 and 8), the formation of methane is significant. On the other hand, due to the exothermic nature of this reaction, the production of methane is not favored with the increase in temperature [10]. Therefore, slightly less methane is produced at 460 °C than at 420 °C whereas the amount of the most desirable products, hydrogen and carbon dioxide, increases. Although, in the case of Co-0.1La/CeO₂ catalyst, there is observed increase in the ethanol conversion from ~60% to ~80% after 21 h of SRE reaction with the increase in temperature from 420 °C (Fig. 5) to 460 °C (Fig. 8a), it is still too low temperature to maintain the stability of the catalyst. Moreover, C₂ and C₃ products are still present in the outlet. Because their formation increases over time whereas ethanol conversion decreases it confirms deactivation of Co-0.1La/CeO₂ catalyst under SRE conditions at 460 °C because of the decrease of the capacity of cobalt active phase for breaking the C–C bond [7]. After 21 h of process, comparable amount of acetone (~30%) is produced both at 420 °C and 460 °C. However, selectivity to acetaldehyde decreases from ~20% to <10% with the increase of temperature. These results suggest that aldol condensation of acetaldehyde (reaction 3) is more favored over Co-0.1La/CeO₂ catalyst at 460 °C than at 420 °C. The further increase in the temperature to 500 °C (Fig. 8b) allows to drastically limit the C₂ and C₃ products and only the acetaldehyde is produced at a trace level up to 0.6% after 21 h of SRE process. Moreover, this temperature is sufficient to obtain complete ethanol conversion and very high selectivity to two main products of SRE reaction, i.e. hydrogen and carbon dioxide, at a constant level of 94% and 88%, respectively during 21 h of process. Compared to these products, the amount of by-products of SRE reaction over Co-0.1La/CeO₂ catalyst at 500 °C, i.e. carbon monoxide and methane, is very low and it almost does not change over time, remaining at level of 10% for both of them. The initial selectivity to hydrogen and all C₁ products over Co-0.1La/CeO₂ catalyst is the same at temperature of 460 °C. But because of the catalyst deactivation at 460 °C, it decrease with the increase of time of SRE reaction to 80%, 52%, 4% and 4% for hydrogen, carbon dioxide, methane and carbon monoxide, respectively. Because cobalt-based catalysts are less active in cleavage of C–C bond than nickel-based samples, Co-0.1La/CeO₂ catalyst is probably not so active toward ethanol decomposition (reaction 5) as Ni-0.1La/CeO₂ [55]. Therefore, it is supposed that mainly ethanol dehydrogenation (reaction 2) followed by acetaldehyde decomposition (reaction 6), WGS reaction (reaction 11) and steam reforming of methane (reaction 9) take place over Co-0.1La/CeO₂ catalyst in the all studied range of temperature from 420 to 460 °C. Moreover, the formation of acetone indicates that aldol condensation of acetaldehyde occurs below 460 °C of SRE process [29,55].

The results obtained for both Co-0.1La/CeO₂ and Ni-0.1La/CeO₂ catalysts indicate that the catalysts deactivation rate decreases with the increase in temperature and more active sites remain available to break C–C and C–H bonds in the ethanol to produce hydrogen and C₁ products. Moreover, the Ni-0.1La/CeO₂ catalyst is stable under SRE conditions at 460 °C whereas Co-0.1La/CeO₂ sample requires higher temperature of 500 °C.

The catalytic performance of Co-0.1La/CeO₂ and Ni-0.1La/CeO₂ catalysts studied in this work in SRE reaction was compared to results obtained for other cobalt- and nickel-based catalysts promoted with lanthanum (Table 4). The experiments were carried out under the different reaction conditions (temperature, feed compositions, time-on-the stream, etc.) which could strongly influence on the activity, selectivity and stability of the catalysts [71]. These studies were conducted at the highest water-to-ethanol molar ratio

of 12 among presented in Table 4. An excess of water was significantly but it corresponded to ethanol-to-water molar ratio of bioethanol produced by fermentation of sugars from plants [18]. Despite the heat provided to carry out the process increased, an increase in water in reactants assisted also the production of hydrogen and carbon dioxide [10]. Indeed, the selectivity to hydrogen and carbon dioxide over Co-0.1La/CeO₂ and Ni-0.1La/CeO₂ catalysts is considerably higher than that obtained in the presence of other catalysts (Table 4). For example, Co/CeO₂-La₂O₃ produced only 66% of hydrogen and 2% of carbon dioxide after 15 h of SRE reaction at 500 °C, at water-to-ethanol molar ratio of 10 [15]. Whereas Ni-La-Ce-C allowed to obtain hydrogen and carbon dioxide with selectivity of 60% and 18%, respectively after 8 h of SRE process at 650 °C, at low water-to-ethanol molar ratio of 3. Comparison of these results with those obtained in these studies, i.e. hydrogen and carbon dioxide selectivity values of 94% and 88%, respectively for Co-0.1La/CeO₂ catalysts at 500 °C and 80% and 68%, respectively for Ni-0.1La/CeO₂ catalyst at 460 °C confirms their excellent performance in SRE reaction. These excellent results were obtained, despite very high value of water/ethanol mixture flow rate (100 ml/min) which was incomparably higher in comparison with the conditions used in the case of other samples promoted with lanthanum (Table 4). Taking into account that water/ethanol mixture in these studies was not dilute with any inert gas, the stability tests of Co-0.1La/CeO₂ and Ni-0.1La/CeO₂ catalysts were carried out under very demanding conditions.

4. Conclusions

The Co-0.1La/CeO₂ and Ni-0.1La/CeO₂ catalysts were obtained by simple, fast and inexpensive co-impregnation method as a potential materials being active, stable and highly selective to hydrogen and carbon dioxide in SRE reaction. Despite small addition of La₂O₃ to the catalyst of 2 wt% corresponding to La/Co(Ni) molar ratio of 0.1, both cobalt- and nickel based catalysts exhibited much better stability, higher ethanol conversion, higher capability to C-C bond cleavage and smaller amount of by-products under SRE conditions at 420 °C than unpromoted catalysts. The superior performance is likely to be related to the improved active metal phase dispersion and enhanced-metal support interaction evidenced by the lower reducibility of cobalt/nickel species by the addition of La₂O₃ as a promoter. Regardless of being promoted with La₂O₃ or not, nickel-based catalysts demonstrate better ability to break of C-C bond, higher activity and stability during SRE process compared to cobalt-based samples. Their lower deactivation rate observed despite the much higher amount of carbon deposit could be attributed formation of filamentous carbon with lower degree of graphitization, i.e. turbostratic structure. The rapid deactivation of the cobalt-based catalysts results from an isolation of cobalt species from ethanol molecules because of their encapsulation by highly ordered carbon deposit. The coverage of cobalt active sites layer by layer by graphitic carbon makes that they could not participate in SRE reaction. The carbon deposit over cobalt- and nickel-based catalysts under SRE conditions differs in types, morphology and degree of graphitization. The addition of La₂O₃ promoter to the Co/CeO₂ and Ni/CeO₂ catalysts does not influence on these properties of carbonaceous deposition. However, its effect on the amount of formed carbon deposits is significant. In case both cobalt- and nickel based catalysts, less carbon is formed over catalysts promoted with La₂O₃ which results from a smaller size of nickel/cobalt crystallites obtained in the presence of the promoter.

Temperature of 460 °C is sufficient to obtain complete ethanol conversion during 21 h of SRE process with very high selectivity to hydrogen (88%) and carbon dioxide (68%) and only two by-products, methane and carbon monoxide, over Ni-0.1La/CeO₂

catalyst. Although the amount of carbon monoxide is low, a formation of methane because of favoring methanation reaction by nickel active phase is rather significant. In the case of Co-0.1La/CeO₂ catalyst, the higher temperature of 500 °C to obtain complete ethanol conversion during 21 h of SRE reaction is required. However, selectivity to hydrogen and carbon dioxide in the presence of this catalyst under these conditions is very high, 94% and 88%, respectively. Besides methane and carbon monoxide produced in low amounts, the acetaldehyde at trace level is detected among by-products of SRE reaction over Co-0.1La/CeO₂ catalyst.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Magdalena Greluk: Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Writing - review & editing. **Marek Rotko:** Methodology, Investigation. **Sylwia Turczyniak-Surdacka:** Methodology, Investigation.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2020.03.117>.

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